

Studies in the Synthesis of Furochromones. Part V

R. J. PATOLIA and K. N. TRIVEDI

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-390 002

Manuscript received 25 June 1979, revised 27 October 1980, accepted 5 November 1980

2-Hydroxy-4-allyloxyacetophenone(Ia), on Claisen condensation with ethyl formate in the presence of sodium gave 2-hydroxy-2,3-dihydro-7-allyloxychromone(IIa), which on dehydration, followed by Claisen rearrangement gave 8-allyl-7-hydroxychromone(IIIb). This on treatment with osmium tetroxide potassium periodate followed by cyclization with PPA yielded 7H-furo(2,3-h)benzopyran-7-one(VIIIa). The synthesis of 2-methyl-7H-furo(2,3-h)benzopyran-7-one(VIIIb) was reported starting from (IIIb) through cyclization followed by dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal. 2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-4-allyloxyacetophenone on similar series of reactions afforded 9-methyl-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran-5-one(IXa) and 2,9-dimethyl-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran-5-one(IXb).

THE chromone derivatives unsubstituted in 2- and 3-positions were rarely reported in the literature and such few derivatives have been recently isolated from nature^{1,2}. It was therefore, thought of interest to synthesise such chromone derivatives. In continuation of our work³, we report here the synthesis of four new furochromones viz. 7H-furo(2,3-h)benzopyran-7-one(VIIIa), 2-methyl-7H-furo(2,3-h)benzopyran-7-one(VIIIb), 9-methyl-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran-5-one(IXa) and 2,9-dimethyl-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran-5-one(IXb).

Claisen condensation of 2-hydroxy-4-allyloxyacetophenone(Ia)⁴ and 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-allyloxyacetophenone(Ib)⁵ with ethyl formate gave cyclic product 2-hydroxy-2,3-dihydro-7-allyloxychromone(IIa) and 2-hydroxy-2,3-dihydro-7-allyloxy-8-methylchromone(IIb) respectively. Their structures were confirmed on the basis of UV, IR and NMR spectra. There was no shift in UV absorption, when recorded by addition of dil. sodium hydroxide solution. In the NMR spectrum, there was absence of aldehydic proton around δ 9.0 and also the signals for methylene protons are not at δ 3.75 but they are quite upfield.

The compounds (IIa) and (IIb) on dehydration with sulphuric acid (30%) followed by Claisen rearrangement in dimethylaniline afforded 7-hydroxy-8-allylchromone(IIIb) and 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methylchromone(IIIc) respectively. (IIIb) and (IIIc), on treatment with osmium tetroxide-potassium periodate⁶ in ethyl acetate-water, followed by cyclization of the acetaldehyde products with polyphosphoric acid gave corresponding 7H-furo(2,3-h)benzopyran-7-one(VIIIa) and 9-methyl-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran-5-one(IXa).

7-Hydroxy-8-allylchromone(IIIb), on trituration with sulphuric acid (85%) yielded 2-methyl-2,3-di-

hydro-7H-furo(2,3-h)benzopyran-7-one(IV), while 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methylchromone(IIIc), under similar condition underwent desired cyclization to furan ring with simultaneous opening of γ -pyrone ring followed by its conversion to 2,3-dihydro-2,7-dimethyl-5-acetyl-6-hydroxybenzofuran(V). This is an unusual case of γ -pyrone ring opening with sulphuric acid. The structure of (V) confirmed by its NMR spectrum (Table 1) and its synthesis from 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-allyloxyacetophenone(Ib), which was subjected to Claisen rearrangement in dimethylaniline followed by cyclization with sulphuric acid (85%).

Dehydrogenation of 2-methyl-2,3-dihydro-7H-furo(2,3-h)benzopyran-7-one(IV) with palladized charcoal (10%) gave 2-methyl-7H-furo(1,3-h)benzopyran-7-one(VIIIb).

Claisen condensation of 2,3-dihydro-2,7-dimethyl-5-acetyl-6-hydroxybenzofuran(V) with ethyl formate in presence of pulverized sodium, gave 2,9-dimethyl-7-hydroxy-2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran-5-one(VI), which was dehydrated to 2,3-dihydro-2,9-dimethyl-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran-5-one(VII), using sulphuric acid (30%). (VII), on dehydrogenation with palladized charcoal (10%), yielded 2,9-dimethyl-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran-5-one(IXb).

- (Ia) $R=R_2=H$, $R_1=-CH_2CH=CH_2$
(Ib) $R=H$, $R_1=-CH_2CH=CH_2$, $R_2=CH_3$
(Ic) $R=-CH_2CH=CH_2$, $R_1=H$, $R_2=CH_3$

- (IIa) $R=R_2=H, R_1=-CH_2CH=CH_2$
 (IIb) $R=H, R_1=-CH_2CH=CH_2, R_2=CH_3$

- (IIIa) $R=R_2=H, R_1=-CH_2CH=CH_2$
 (IIIb) $R=R_2=H, R_1=-CH_2CH=CH_2$
 (IIIc) $R=H, R_1=-CH_2CH=CH_2, R_2=OH$
 (IIId) $R=-CH_2CH=CH_2, R_1=H, R_2=CH_3$

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

(VII)

(IX a) $R=H$ (IX b) $R=CH_3$

Experimental

NMR spectra were recorded on 90 MHz and 220 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. IR spectra (nujol) were determined on Perkin-Elmer 457 spectrophotometer. UV spectra were recorded on Beckmann DU-2 spectrophotometer and λ_{max} values in nm and $\log \epsilon$ values are given in parenthesis.

2-Hydroxy-2,3-dihydro-7-allyloxychromone (IIa) :

The solution of 2-hydroxy-4-allyloxyacetophenone (Ia)⁴ (3.8 g) in ethyl formate (22 ml) was allowed to react slowly with powdered sodium (2.3 g)

kept in dry ether (8 ml) at 20° for 1 hr. More ethyl formate (10 ml) was added slowly and the reaction mixture was refluxed in a water bath at 55° for 15 minutes. It was then left overnight. Alcohol and water were successively added with care and the resulting alkaline solution was extracted twice with ether. The aqueous alkaline layer was acidified with acetic acid. A crystalline yellow solid separated slowly was filtered and washed with water. It crystallized from benzene as needles, m.p. 154° (decom.), yield 2.5 g, 57%. It gave a pale brownish violet colour with ethanolic ferric chloride and on standing fastness of the colour increased. (Found : C, 65.9; H, 5.7 $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 65.5; H, 5.5%); $UV\lambda_{max}^{MeOH}$: 272 (4.51), 311 (4.21); MeOH + NaOH : 272(4.50), 311(4.29); IR : 3225 cm^{-1} (-OH), 1650 ($>C=O$).

2-Hydroxy-2,3-dihydro-7-allyloxy-8-methylchromone (Iib) m.p. 131° (decom.); (Found : C, 66.6; H, 5.8 $C_{13}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 66.7; H, 5.9); $UV\lambda_{max}^{MeOH}$: 282(4.55), MeOH + NaOH : 278 (4.33), IR : 3170 (-OH), 1650 ($>C=O$); and 2,9-dimethyl-7-hydroxy-2,3,6,7-tetrahydro-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran-5-one (VI), m.p. 138° (decom.); (Found : C, 67.1; H, 5.7 $C_{13}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 66.7; H, 6.0%); IR : 3335 cm^{-1} (-OH), 1672 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$) were prepared accordingly from 2-hydroxy 3-methyl-4-allyloxyacetophenone (Ib) and 2,3-dihydro-2,7-dimethyl-5-acetyl-6-hydroxybenzofuran (V) respectively.

7-Allyloxychromone (IIIa) :

2-Hydroxy-2,3-dihydro-7-allyloxychromone (2 g) was taken in sulphuric acid (30%; 60 ml) and heated on a water bath for 2 hr. On cooling, the white crystalline product was separated, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water. It crystallized as colourless shining rectangular rods from a mixture of benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 84°, yield 1.6 g, 88% (Found : C, 71.5; H, 5.1 $C_{12}H_{10}O_3$ requires, C, 71.3; H, 5.0%).

The compound (IIIc), m.p. 79° (Found : C, 72.3; H, 5.4 $C_{13}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 72.2; H, 5.6%) and (VII), m.p. 121° (Found : C, 72.1; H, 5.5 $C_{13}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 72.2; H, 5.6%) were prepared from (Iib) and (VI) respectively according to the method described above.

7-Hydroxy-8-allylchromone (IIIb) :

7-Allyloxychromone (1.5 g) was refluxed with dimethylaniline (12 ml) for 8 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual. The product crystallized from aqueous ethanol as colourless needles, m.p. 184°, yield 1.2 g, 80% (Found : C, 71.6; H, 5.5 $C_{12}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 71.3; H, 5.0%); IR : 3145 cm^{-1} (-OH) and 1645 cm^{-1} ($>C=O$).

TABLE 1—¹H NMR SPECTRA* OF IIa, IIb*, IIIa, IV, V, VII, VIIIa, VIIIb, IXa AND IXb

Compound	Solvent	C-2	C-3	C-4	C-5	C-6	C-7	C-8	C-9
IIa	DMSO-d ₆	5.78(m, 1H) 7.55(d, J=7 ; -OH)	2.74 (m, 2H)	—	7.65 (d, J=10 ; 1H)	6.64 (d, J=10 ; 1H)	Allyloxy group	6.52 (s, 1H)	—
IIb*	CdCl ₂	5.92 (t, J=5.2 ; 1H)	2.95 (m, 2H)	—	7.80 (d, J=9 ; 1H)	6.60 (d, J=9 ; 1H)	Allyloxy group	2.11 (s, 3H, -CH ₃)	—
IIIa	CdCl ₂	7.78 (d, J=7 ; 1H)	6.25 (d, J=7 1H)	—	8.10 (d, J=9, 1H)	6.96 (dd, J=9, 1.4 ; 1H)	Allyloxy group	6.82 (d, J=1.4 ; 1H)	—
IV	CdCl ₂	1.55 (d, J=6 ; 3H, -CH ₃)	3.22 (m, 2H)	—	7.72 (d, J=6 ; 1H)	6.28 (d, J=6 ; 1H)	—	8.14 (d, J=9, 1H)	6.78 (d, J=9 ; 1H)
V	CdCl ₂	1.44 (d, J=6 ; 3H, -CH ₃)	2.62 (m, 2H)	7.19 (s, 1H)	2.20 (s, 3H, -COCH ₃)	—	2.45 (s, 3H -CH ₃)	—	—
VII	CdCl ₂	1.49 (d, J=7 ; 3H, -CH ₃)	3.04 (m, 2H)	7.76 (s, 1H)	—	6.18 (d, J=7, 1H)	7.70 (d, J=7 ; 1H)	—	2.24 (s, 3H, -CH ₃)
VIIIa	CdCl ₂	7.72 (d, J=1.8 ; 1H)	7.08 (d, J=1.8 ; 1H)	—	7.90 (d, J=6 ; 1H)	6.38 (d, J=6, 1H)	—	8.13 (d, J=10 ; 1H)	7.52 (d, J=10 ; 1H)
VIIIb	CdCl ₂	2.52 (s, 3H, -CH ₃)	6.67 (s, 1H)	—	7.88 (d, J=6 ; 1H)	6.36 (d, J=6 ; 1H)	—	8.03 (d, J=9 ; 1H)	7.41 (d, J=9 ; 1H)
IXa	CdCl ₂	7.71 (d, J=1.8 ; 1H)	6.88 (d, J=1.8 ; 1H)	8.30 (s, 1H)	—	6.92 (d, J=6 ; 1H)	7.92 (d, J=6 ; 1H)	—	2.62 (s, 3H, -CH ₃)
IXb	CdCl ₂	2.45 (s, 3H, -CH ₃)	6.35 (s, 1H)	8.01 (s, 1H)	—	6.23 (d, J=6.5 ; 1H)	7.78 (d, J=6.5 1H)	—	2.55 (s, 3H, -CH ₃)

* Chemical shifts in δ and coupling constants in Hz,
* Recorded on 220 MHz spectrometer.

This method was employed to 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-allyloxyacetophenone(Ib) and 7-allyloxy-8-methylchromone(IIIc) to give 2,4-dihydroxy-3-methyl-5-allylacetophenone(Ic), m.p. 139° (Found : C, 70.1 ; H, 7.0 C₁₅H₁₄O₃ requires C, 70.6 ; H, 6.9%), IR : 3330 cm⁻¹ (-OH), 1636 cm⁻¹ (>C=O) and 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methylchromone(IIId), m.p. 141° (Found : C, 72.4 ; H, 5.6 C₁₅H₁₂O₃ requires C, 72.2 ; H, 5.6%) ; IR : 3280 cm⁻¹ (-OH), 1640 cm⁻¹ (>C=O) respectively.

7H-Furo(2,3-h)benzopyran-7-one(VIIIa) :

7-Hydroxy-8-allylchromone (0.6 g) in ethyl acetate (120 ml) and osmium tetroxide (60 mg) in water (50 ml) were vigorously stirred for 15 minutes. Potassium periodate (1.7 g) was added in small quantities to the dark solution over a period of 3 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual. The residue 8-acetaldehyde product was taken in PPA (15 ml) and heated in an oil bath for 1.5 hr at 115°. The crude product was dissolved in chloroform (2 ml) and percolated through a column of silica gel. Elution with a mixture of benzene-chloroform (9 : 1), yielded (VIIIa). It crystallized from a mixture of benzene-petroleum ether as colourless prisms, m.p. 186°,

yield 0.18 g, 33% (Found : C, 71.2 ; H, 3.5 C₁₁H₈O₂ requires C, 71.0 ; H, 3.2%).

Similarly(IXa), m.p. 186-7° (Found : C, 72.2 ; H, 4.2 C₁₅H₈O₃ requires C, 72.0 ; H, 4.0%) ; UV λ_{max}^{MeOH} : 239 (4.94), 322 (4.16) was prepared from (IIId).

2-Methyl-2,3-dihydro-7H-furo(2,3-h)benzopyran-7-one(IV) :

7-Hydroxy-8-allylchromone (1 g) was triturated with sulphuric acid (85% ; 8 ml) in a water bath for 15 minutes. The contents were poured into crushed ice, the product separated was filtered and washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution. It crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether as pale yellow coloured prisms, m.p. 136°, yield 0.79, 70%. (Found : C, 71.1 ; H, 5.2 C₁₂H₁₀O₃ requires C, 71.3 ; H.5.0%).

The compound(V), m.p. 104° (Found : C, 70.1 ; H, 6.7 C₁₂H₁₄O₃ requires C, 69.9 ; H, 6.7%) ; IR : 1645 cm⁻¹ (-COCH₃), 1620, 1403, 1337, 1182, 874, 860, 769 cm⁻¹ was similarly obtained from (Ic). While 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methylchromone (IIId)

on similar treatment of sulphuric acid (85%), did not give (VII), but gave the product, which was identical (m.p. 104°, mixed m.p. 104° and IR) with (V); (Found : C, 69.8 ; H, 6.9 $C_{12}H_{14}O_8$ requires C, 69.9 ; H, 6.7%).

2-Methyl-7H-furo(2,3-h)benzopyran-7-one(VIIIb) :

2-Methyl-2,3-dihydro-7H-furo(2,3-h)benzopyran-7-one (0.4 g) was refluxed in diphenyl ether (7 ml) with palladized charcoal (10% ; 0.6 g) for 9 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and the solvent was removed by steam distillation. It crystallized from aqueous ethanol as colourless needles, m.p. 152°, yield 0.25 g, 62%. (Found : C, 71.7 ; H, 4.3 $C_{12}H_8O_8$ requires C, 72.0 ; H, 4.0%).

UV λ_{max}^{MeOH} : 240 (4.69), 250 (4.64), 306 (4.09).

Similarly (IXb), m.p. 188-9° (Found : C, 73.4 ; H, 4.8 $C_{13}H_{10}O_8$ requires C, 72.9 ; H, 4.7%).

UV λ_{max}^{MeOH} : 244 (4.95), 328 (4.19) was prepared from (VII).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. F. M. Dean, Department of Organic Chemistry, the Robert Robinson Laboratories, Liverpool and Dr. Sukh Dev, Director, Malti Chem Research Centre, Nandesari, Baroda for NMR spectra, Prof. E. Gellert, Wollongong University, Wollongong, Australia for IR spectra, Dr. S.S Lele for the micro analysis of the compounds and the UGC, New Delhi for the award of a Research Fellowship to one of us (R.J.P).

References

1. R. PENDSE, A. V. R. RAO and K. VENKATARAMAN, *Phytochemistry*, 1973, **12**, 2033.
2. G. ROMUSSI and G. CIARALLO, *Phytochemistry*, 1974, **13**, 2890.
3. R. J. PATOLIA and K. N. TRIVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* (In press).
4. W. BAKER and O. M. LOTHIAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 628 ; 1936, 274.
5. V. N. DHOLAKIA and K. N. TRIVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 1058.
6. S. K. MUKERJEE, M. M. RAO and T. R. SESHADRI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, **6**, 1.